

FURANO COMPOUNDS. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF FURO-3'-METHYL-5:6 (4':5')-COUMARIN AND FURO-3'-ETHYL-5:6 (4':5')-COUMARIN.

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Ethyl 5-hydroxy-6-acetylcoumarin-3-carboxylate on condensation with ethyl bromoacetate affords ethyl 3-carbethoxy-6-acetylcoumarin-5-O-acetic ester, which on subsequent hydrolysis and ring-closure affords furo-3'-methyl-5:6 (4':5')-coumarin-3-carboxylic acid. The foregoing acid on decarboxylation affords furo-3'-methyl-5:6 (4':5')-coumarin. Similarly furo-3'-ethyl-5:6 (4':5')-coumarin was synthesised starting from ethyl 5-hydroxy-6-propionylcoumarin-3-carboxylate.

Furocoumarins, derived from 5-hydroxycoumarin, are not known with the exception of 3:4'-dimethyl-5':6'-furocoumarin synthesised by Kelkar and Ranade (*Rasayanam*, 1938, 1, 151) by condensation of 5-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin (Sethna, Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228) with ethyl bromoacetate, subsequent hydrolysis and ring-closure. However, furocoumarins, unsubstituted in the 4-position, cannot be obviously prepared by this method.

As a part of the comprehensive investigation of the synthetical possibilities of 2:4-dihydroxy-3-formylacetophenone (Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 132 and subsequent papers) and other ketone-aldehydes, we have synthesised furo-3'-methyl-5:6-(4':5')-coumarin and furo-3'-ethyl-5:6(4':5')-coumarin.

Ethyl 5-hydroxy-6-acetylcoumarin-3-carboxylate (I, R=Me; R'=Et) (Shah and Shah, *loc. cit.*), now prepared by the esterification of 5-hydroxy-6-acetylcoumarin-3-carboxylic acid, on condensation with ethyl bromoacetate in acetone solution in presence of potassium carbonate affords ethyl 3-carbethoxy-6-acetylcoumarin-5-O-acetic ester (II, R=Me; R'=Et). On hydrolysis with dilute alkali (II) gives 3-carboxy-6-acetylcoumarin-5-O-acetic acid (II, R=Me; R'=H), which on treatment with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride affords furo-3'-methyl-5:6(4':5')-coumarin-carboxylic acid (III, R=Me; R'=H). On decarboxylation with quinoline copper

bronze (III) gives furo-3'-methyl-5:6 (4':5')-coumarin (IV, R=Me). The synthesis of the furocoumarin incidentally establishes the structure assigned to ethyl 5-hydroxy-6-acetylcoumarin-3-carboxylate on account of its positive ferric chloride reaction (Shah and Shah, *loc. cit.*).

Similarly from ethyl 5-hydroxy-6-propionylcoumarin-3-carboxylate (I, R=Et; R'=Et) furo-3'-ethyl-5:6 (4':5')-coumarin (IV, R=Et) has been synthesised through the stages: ethyl 3-carbethoxy-6-propionylcoumarin-5-O-acetic ester (II, R=R'=Et), 3-carboxyl-6-propionylcoumarin-5-O-acetic acid (II, R=Et; R'=H), furo-3'-ethyl-5:6 (4':5')-coumarin-3-carboxylic acid (III, R=Et; R'=H).

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Ethyl 5-Hydroxy-6-acetylcoumarin-3-carboxylate (I, R=Me; R'=Et).—A mixture of 5-hydroxy-6-acetylcoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (Shah and Shah, *loc. cit.*) (13 g.), ethyl alcohol (260 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 18 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and the straw-coloured solid separating was filtered and washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate to remove the unchanged acid. The product crystallised from alcohol in straw-coloured plates (12 g.), m. p. 155-56°. Shah and Shah (*loc. cit.*) gave m. p. 155-56°.

Ethyl 3-Carbethoxy-6-acetylcoumarin-5-O-acetic Ester (II, R=Me; R'=Et).—The coumarin ester (5 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (5 g.) and fused potassium carbonate (5 g.) in acetone (300 c.c.) were heated under reflux for 18 hours, the solution filtered and the residue washed thoroughly with acetone (50 c.c.). Acetone and excess of ethyl bromoacetate were removed in a current of air and the solid obtained crystallised from alcohol as pale yellow clusters of needles, m.p. 113-15°. (Found: C, 59.7; H, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 59.7; H, 5.0 per cent).

3-Carboxyl-6-acetylcoumarin-5-O-acetic Acid (II, R=Me; R'=H).—A suspension of the preceding compound (1 g.) was hydrolysed in 4% sodium hydroxide solution (20 c.c.) by heating on the steam-bath for 30 minutes. 3-Carboxy-6-acetylcoumarin-5-O-acetic acid, isolated by acidifi-

cation, was crystallised from hot water in colourless woolly needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 189-91° (decomp.). (Found: C, 55.2; H, 3.3. $C_{14}H_{10}O_8$ requires C, 54.9; H, 3.3 per cent). It is easily soluble in alcohol and hot water.

Furo-3'-methyl-5:6(4':5')-coumarin-3-carboxylic Acid (III, R=Me; R'=H).—A mixture of the foregoing acid (0.5 g.), fused sodium acetate (5 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into water (200 c.c.) and the precipitated pale yellow solid collected and crystallised first from dilute alcohol and then from water in tiny shining pale yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 226-28° (decomp.). (Found: C, 63.6; H, 3.4. $C_{13}H_8O_8$ requires C, 63.9; H, 3.3 per cent). It is easily soluble in alcohol and sparingly in water.

3'-Methyl-5:6(4':5')-furocoumarin (IV, R=Me).—The foregoing acid (0.2 g.) was boiled with quinoline (10 c.c.) containing copper bronze (0.5 g.) for 45 minutes. The filtered solution was mixed with an excess of dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether, the extract washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and evaporated. The residual furo-3'-methyl-5:6(4':5')-coumarin was crystallised from hot water in colourless woolly needles, m.p. 138-40°. (Found: C, 71.7; H, 4.2. $C_{12}H_8O_8$ requires C, 72.0; H, 4.0 per cent). It is insoluble in cold sodium hydroxide solution.

Ethyl 5-Hydroxy-6-propionylcoumarin-3-carboxylate (I, R=Et; R'=Et).—A mixture of 5-hydroxy-6-propionylcoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (6 g.), ethyl alcohol (100 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (6 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 18 hours and the ester isolated as before and crystallised from alcohol in straw-coloured slender pointed needles, m.p. 152-54°. (Found: C, 62.0; H, 5.0. $C_{15}H_{14}O_8$ requires C, 62.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

Ethyl 3-Carboxy-6-propionylcoumarin-5-O-acetic Ester (R=Et; R'=Et).—The coumarin ester (5 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (5 c.c.) and potassium carbonate (5 g.) in acetone (200 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 18 hours, the solution filtered and the residue washed thoroughly with acetone (50 c.c.). Acetone and excess of ethyl bromoacetate were removed in a current of air and the solid obtained crystallised from alcohol as colourless clusters of needles (2 g.), m.p. 103-5°. (Found: C, 60.7; H, 5.4. $C_{13}H_{12}O_8$ requires C, 60.6; H, 5.3 per cent).

3-Carboxyl-6-propionylcoumarin 5-O-acetic Acid (II, R=Et; R'=H).—A suspension of the preceding compound (1 g.) in 4% sodium hydroxide solution (20 c.c.) was heated on the steam-bath for 30 minutes. The acid, isolated with dilute hydrochloric acid, was crystallised from hot water in colourless needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 194-96°. (Found: C, 56.3; H, 3.8. $C_{15}H_{12}O_8$ requires C, 56.3; H, 3.8 per cent).

Furo-3'-ethyl-5:6 (4':5')-coumarin-3-carboxylic Acid (III, R=Et; R'=H).—A mixture of the foregoing acid (0.5 g.), fused sodium acetate (2.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 1 hour and the separated yellow solid collected. It crystallised from water containing a few drops of alcohol in shining, slender, yellow needles, m.p. 157-58°. (Found: C, 61.0; H, 4.50. $C_{14}H_{10}O_3$, H_2O requires C, 60.9 H, 4.4 per cent).

Furo-3'-ethyl-5:6(4':5')-coumarin (IV, R=Et).—The foregoing acid (0.2 g.) was boiled with quinoline (10 c.c.) containing copper bronze (0.4 g.) for 45 minutes. The filtered solution was mixed with an excess of dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether, the extract washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and evaporated. The residual furocoumarin crystallised from hot water in colourless wooly needles, m.p. 150-52°. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 4.9. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 72.9; H, 4.7 per cent).

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